

Interpretable Visual Feature Discovery using Multiple Instance Learning: A Case Study of Colonial Korean Print

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This paper explores how neural networks, particularly Multiple Instance Learning (MIL), can advance computational analysis of historical visual materials. While *Distant Viewing* (Arnold and Tilton, 2023a) has shown how computer vision can analyze visual materials at scale, interpreting how these models identify distinctive features remains a key methodological challenge. Although deep learning approaches achieve high classification accuracy, understanding which visual elements inform their decisions is often unclear, limiting their utility for humanities research where interpretability is crucial. We address this challenge through an innovative application of Multiple Instance Learning to historical print analysis. Using colonial Korean printshops (1910-1945) as our case study, we demonstrate how MIL's interpretable architecture can reveal distinctive visual features while maintaining classification accuracy (Cai *et al.*, 2024). This approach allows us to examine not just what distinguishes different printshops' outputs, but specifically which typographic elements and patterns the model uses to make these distinctions. Drawing on a large digitized corpus from four major colonial Korean printshops, we demonstrate how MIL, originally developed for medical imaging analysis, can effectively classify and help interpret historical visual materials. The model achieves 92% accuracy while providing interpretable attention maps that highlight historically meaningful features. The results demonstrate how computational methods can reveal subtle but consistent variations in common textual elements, such as the rendering of *ieung* (ㅇ) in frequently occurring grammatical particles (*josa* 조사) or the bottom of the *tigut* (ㄷ). This methodological contribution extends beyond Korean print history, offering a framework for interpretable computational analysis of visual materials more broadly.

Colonial Korean printshops present a case study for developing interpretable neural network approaches to visual analysis. During this formative period, when Korean typography and print design were being standardized, print activity grew despite significant economic constraints (De Fremery, 2011; Ryu, 2015). The high cost of mechanical printing equipment and a relatively small market meant printshops typically operated with limited typefaces and resources. Yet even within these constraints, major printshops produced visually distinct outputs through subtle variations in typographic practices - from character spacing and stroke weights to the specific rendering of letter components. While scholars have identified some of these distinctions through close examination of individual texts (De Fremery, 2011; 2014), systematically analyzing such subtle typographic features across thousands of pages has proven challenging. Our study leverages neural networks' classification capabilities to discover and analyze these specific visual features that characterize each printshop's typographic style.

To systematically analyze printshop-specific visual features, we used a corpus of printed materials from each facility. Through the digitization efforts of Hyundam Mun'go archives (Hyundam Mun'go Foundation, 2021), we identified the four most productive printshops of colonial Korea and collected their surviving output. The dataset comprises 66,277 page images, distributed across these facilities as shown in Table 1. This distribution reflects the varying scales of operation and digitization - from *Taedong Inswaeso's* dominant 42.07% share of the analyzed pages to *Chosŏn Inswae Chusik Hoeisa's* more modest 9.21%. These differences in production volume make our dataset particularly interesting:

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despite varying scales of operation and digitization, could these printshops maintain consistent visual styles? And can our computational approach detect these styles regardless of a facility’s output volume?

Printshop	Printshop (KR)	Pages	Percentage
Taedong Inswaeso	大東印刷所	27,882	42.07%
Hansŏng Toso Chusik Hoeisa	漢城圖書株式會社	19,244	29.04%
Sinmungwan	新文館	13,050	19.69%
Chosŏn Inswae chusik Hoeisa	朝鮮印刷株式會社	6,101	9.20%
Total		66,277	100%

Table 1: Distribution of analyzed pages across the four most productive colonial Korean printshops.

In this study, we tested three different approaches to printshop classification, building on recent work in computational analysis of historical print (Seuret *et al.*, 2019; Im, Kim and Mandl, 2022). Initial experiments used a ConvNext Base architecture for full-page analysis, following successful applications of pre-trained architectures to historical font classification. This approach achieved 98% accuracy (F1=0.98) in classifying printshop origins. However, Grad-CAM (Selvaraju *et al.*, 2020) visualizations revealed the model primarily focused on page margins rather than typographic content - displaying a high likelihood of overfitting.

To address this limitation, we adopted Seuret *et al.* (2019) approach of training on random page cutouts, forcing the model to look beyond margins and mitigate overfitting. A Swin S3 Base-224 model (Liu *et al.*, 2021) achieved the highest performance (99.8% accuracy, F1=0.99), visual inspection again revealed overfitting - the model relied on seemingly random or uninterpretable features rather than meaningful typographic patterns. This highlighted our core challenge: how to develop models that not only classify accurately but reveal meaningful visual patterns that can inform humanities research.

Figure 1: Examples of full page images with correct identification and their Grad-CAM rollout.

Figure 2: Examples of random page cutouts with correct identification and their Grad-CAM rollout.

Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) proved most suitable for our task, achieving 92% accuracy ($F_1=0.92$) while providing interpretable insights into which visual features inform its classifications. Originally developed for medical image analysis to help both classify and locate malignant parts of cells such as tumors in diagnostic images, MIL’s dual focus on accuracy and interpretable localization directly parallels our needs in humanities research. We adapted an attribute-driven attention-based MIL model (Cai *et al.*, 2024) that processes each page as a “bag of instances” - acknowledging that not all parts of an image are equally informative.

The model’s architecture incorporates two specialized constraints that enhance interpretability. A spatial attribute constraint enforces consistency by encouraging similar attribute scores for adjacent patches that share visual features. This helps maintain coherent attention patterns across regions with similar typographic or layout characteristics. The attribute ranking constraint ensures features receive higher scores only when they are truly distinctive of a particular printshop rather than common across all facilities. This helps the model focus on elements that meaningfully distinguish one printshop from another, rather than generic features of printed pages. Together, these constraints allow us to not only achieve accurate classification but also understand which visual elements (e.g. typographical) separate each printshop’s output.

Our implementation of MIL involved training on images resized to 896×896 pixels, divided into 16×16 pixel patches. Training for 100 epochs with a batch size of 128, we employed the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of $1e-4$ and an adaptive learning rate scheduler that reduced the rate by a factor of 0.1 after 10 epochs without improvement. We conducted two sets of experiments: one with 16×16 pixel patches and another with 8×8 pixel patches while maintaining other parameters.

Figure 3: Multi-Instance Learning pipeline.

To validate the model’s feature detection and assess the interpretability of identified typographic patterns, we employ established embedding-based approaches. The effectiveness of embedding spaces for grouping visually similar elements has been well-demonstrated in research (Wevers and Smits, 2020; Arnold and Tilton, 2023b; Smits and Wevers, 2023). The applicability of such embedding techniques to typographic analysis finds precedent in computer vision research, particularly through studies of the MNIST handwritten character dataset (Lecun *et al.*, 1998), where embedding spaces consistently demonstrate robust clustering of visually similar letterforms (Google, 2024).

Our evaluation methodology focuses on analyzing the high-attention patches identified by our MIL model’s attribute-driven attention mechanism. From these identified regions, we extract embeddings directly from our trained MIL model’s feature representations, leveraging the learned visual characteristics that the model has developed through its printshop classification training.

Our analysis pipeline employs a systematic approach to clustering and visualization. We first extract high-dimensional embeddings from the MIL model for all sampled patches, then apply dimensionality

reduction using UMAP (McInnes, Healy and Melville, 2020) to create 2D representations suitable for visualization and clustering. For clustering, we implement HDBSCAN (Campello, Moulavi and Sander, 2013) to identify coherent visual groupings within the embedding space.

Figure 4: Visualization of UMAP embedding space.

Initial manual inspection reveals distinct clustering patterns at different patch scales. With 16×16 pixel patches, we observe clustering around complete syllabic components, particularly high-frequency grammatical particles (*josa* 조사) such as *üi* (의) and *e* (에). Analysis at 8×8 pixels reveals more granular patterns centered on specific character components, as shown in Figure 5, where we observe consistent clustering around the consonant *ieung* (ㅇ) and the bottom stroke of *tigut* (ㄷ). Further granular analysis was not conducted, as the metal matrices used by these printshops embodied typographic distinctions at the level of strokes and components rather than finer details.

These findings around the stroke of *tigut* align with De Fremery (2011) - particularly in the variations detected in the weight and axis of strokes. This analysis is exemplified in Figure 6, which illustrates printshop-specific variations in rendering the syllable *ta* (ㄷㅏ). The extracted features align with visible typographic distinctions - both Taedong Inswaesoo and Sinnungwan demonstrate a characteristic angled bottom stroke in their *tigut* (ㄷ) renderings, a feature absent in samples from other printshops. This correspondence between our model’s detected patches and complete syllabic renderings demonstrates how our computational approach captures typographic variations at historically meaningful scales of analysis.

Figure 5: Taedong Inswaesoo extracted patches.

Figure 6: Examples of *ieung* (ㅇ) & the syllable *Ta* (ㅏ) from various print shops.

Although our model demonstrates strong classification performance (92% accuracy, $F1=0.92$) and provides interpretable attention maps, it remains important to establish reliable quantitative metrics for evaluating these typographic features in the future. Our findings suggest that effective computational analysis of historical materials depends heavily on examining frequently occurring elements rather than distinctive ones - the subtle but consistent variations in how printshops rendered components become detectable through careful computational analysis.

This study demonstrates Multiple Instance Learning’s potential for addressing the crucial challenge of interpretability in computational humanities research. While developed for medical imaging analysis, MIL’s emphasis on interpretable feature detection proves particularly valuable for humanities scholars who require both systematic analysis and understanding of model decisions. The success in discovering typographic variations through attention-driven feature analysis suggests broader applications in computational humanities research, particularly where visual distinctions may be subtle and distinguishing features unknown to researchers at the outset.

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